

Blockchain and the music industry" and "Hacker meets Security".

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Abstract

Keywords:

1. Introduction

Joshua started doing business at a young age. Born in an enterprising family, father with his own international port company and mother a communication agency. Joshua was 16 years old when he sold his first ICT company. After selling his first company he already started working in the tourism / events industry. Until last year, when Joshua mapped out problems within the events sector and invented the concept of Fissacoin, in which the biggest problem within the sector could be tackled.

Author biography

Joshua Hiwat At the moment Joshua has been working professionally as a software programmer for 5 years. Customers for which he worked: Amazon, Partyflock, Tax Administration (government), Spie Netherlands International.

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